

Strategies for Preserving Layers of History on Apollo-Era Flown engines

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Abstract

In March 2013, 25,000 pounds (12.5 tons) of Apollo-era (1969-1972) Saturn V rocket engine parts were recovered off the coast of Florida after more than 40 years on the floor of the Atlantic Ocean. The expedition was sponsored by Jeff Bezos, Amazon's founder and chief executive, with the support of NASA.

The engine parts were recovered from a debris field of 300 square miles at a depth of approximately 14,000 feet (4,300 meters) using deep-sea sonar and remote operated vehicles. The recovery initiated exceptional press coverage and launched an unprecedented conservation project to preserve the most powerful liquid-fueled yet disposal engines that were ever made.

This presentation will discuss the technical challenges faced in preserving complex artifacts made from a combination of super-alloys and other modern materials, many of which are unfamiliar to conservators, and address how the treatment was able to preserve traces of use and the passage of these artifacts through time. These traces include mission identification stencils, self-adhesive labels that were observed during the documentation process; evidence of engine use such as accumulated soot on the combustion chambers and specific coloration such as bluing still visible on certain parts of the engines; evidence of deformation of the engines upon impact with the water; corrosion stains or patterns indicating the position of the object in the sediment.

This presentation will show how applying the right degree of cleaning to each object using a combination of techniques was deemed critical to their long-term preservation, historical significance, and the aesthetic appeal of the collection as a whole. The paper will also demonstrate how a multidisciplinary dialogue was key to the success of the project and prompted effective integration of conservation theory and practice to identify, preserve and interpret this remarkable collection of modern aerospace heritage.